

AN ANALYSIS OF SOCIO - ECONOMIC AND ENTREPRENEURIAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE MANGO GROWERS IN SALEM DISTRICT OF TAMIL NADU

N. Manivannan* & M. Natarajan**

* Assistant Professor, Department of Agricultural Extension, School of Agricultural Sciences, Bharath Institute of Higher Education and Research, Selaiyur, Tambaram, Chennai, Tamil Nadu

** Assistant Professor, Department of Agricultural Extension, Faculty of Agriculture, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar, Tamil Nadu

Cite This Article: N. Manivannan & M. Natarajan, "An Analysis of Socio - Economic and Entrepreneurial Characteristics of the Mango Growers in Salem District of Tamil Nadu", International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research, Volume 9, Issue 2, July - December, Page Number 1-4, 2024.

Copy Right: © DV Publication, 2024 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

The study was carried out with the objectives of entrepreneurial performance of mango growers in Salem district of Tamil Nadu. The research was taken-up in Salem district of Tamil Nadu. Out of the twenty blocks in Salem District, Sankari Block was chosen based on the largest area under mango cultivation. A sample size of 120 mango-cultivating farmers was selected by using the proportionate random sampling technique. The required data were collected by personal interview utilizing a well-structured and pre-tested interview schedule. The result revealed that the Majority of the respondents were middle-aged (50.00 per cent) and possessed formal education (78.33 per cent). They had subsidiary occupations along with farming (70.00 per cent) with medium level of experience in mango cultivation (65.00 per cent). They had small farm size (58.33 per cent) with low annual income (55.00 per cent). They had low area under mango cultivation (80.00 per cent) with possesses medium level of farm power (51.67 per cent). They had medium levels of social participation (71.67 per cent), extension agency contact (50.00 per cent), mass media exposure (55.00 per cent), training programmes attended (58.33 per cent) and scientific orientation (51.67 per cent). The findings on entrepreneurial performance may help the farmers to develop appropriate strategies for utilising effective technology in mango production and this in turn will show the positive result in the overall development of rural population.

Key Words: Socio-Economic Characteristics, Entrepreneurial Characteristics, Entrepreneurial Behaviour, Mango Growers.

Introduction:

Agriculture is the Indian economy's backbone. Hence, India is also called as an agriculture-dominated country. Development of an economy depends primarily on the critical role of the entrepreneur. Their importance is much more vital in a developing country like India, where many opportunities for using innovations are available to exploit the enterprise resources. Thus, emphasis economic development activity is being given on entrepreneurship of farmers towards the development of their socio-economic welfare. Entrepreneur plays a pivotal role in catalysing economic growth of our country and the same is recognized by global economic growth. Agriculture oriented occupations promote our national economy and many occupations are becoming more complex and complicated for their development of entrepreneurial ability. All these factors attempt them to develop of entrepreneurship on the part of farmers to survive and succeed in the present day as an entrepreneur with a new challenge by facing majority of the agro-related business competition and solve the barriers of the social welfare. Mango is the most important fruit crop in India, with a long history of cultural, socioeconomic, and religious significance. It ranks first among all fruits in terms of area and production in India. Salem district in Tamil Nadu is the prominent region which is involves the farmers in mango cultivation and fruit processing activity. Processing units and marketers of the Mango fruits make a thriving and profitable business as ripe mangoes that are rich in variety and tastes also demands around Tami Nadu. All these factors call for the development of entrepreneurship on the part of farmers to survive and succeed in the present day world competition. Keeping these considerations in mind, the study's objectives were established.

Methodology:

The research was carried out in the Tamil Nadu district of Salem. Sankari block was chosen from among the twenty blocks in Salem district because it has the most area under mango cultivation. The proportionate random sampling technique was used to select a sample size of 120 mango cultivating farmers. Personal interviews were used to collect the necessary data, which followed a well-structured and pre-tested interview schedule. The information gathered was tabulated and analysed using appropriate statistical tools. Thirteen socio-economic variables were selected viz., age, educational status, occupation, annual income, farm size, experience in mango cultivation, area under mango cultivation, farm power possession, social participation, extension agency contact, mass media exposure, training programmes attended and scientific orientation. The respondents were categorised into low, medium and high by using the cumulative frequency method under percentage analysis.

Findings and Discussion:

The results of the study on the personal, socio-economic and entrepreneurial characteristics of mango growers are presented below.

Table: 1. Distribution of the Respondents According to the Socio-Economic and Entrepreneurial Characteristics of the Mango Growers (n=120)

S.No	Category	Number of Respondents	Percent
Age			
1	Young	24	20.00
2	Middle	60	50.00

3	Old	36	30.00
Educational Status			
1	Illiterate	08	06.67
2	Functionally Literate	18	15.00
3	Primary Education	30	25.00
4	Secondary Education	36	30.00
5	Higher Secondary Education	24	20.00
6	Collegiate Education	04	03.33
Occupational Status			
1	Crop Enterprise Alone	36	30.00
2	Crop Enterprise + Any Other Subsidiary Occupation	84	70.00
Annual Income			
1	Low	66	55.00
2	Medium	42	35.00
3	High	12	10.00
Farm Size			
1	Marginal Farm (Upto 2.50 Acres)	20	16.67
2	Small Farm (2.51 To 5 Acres)	70	58.33
3	Big Farm (More Than 5 Acres)	30	25.00
Experience in Mango Cultivation			
1	Low	34	28.33
2	Medium	78	65.00
3	High	08	06.67
Area Under Mango Cultivation			
1	Low	96	80.00
2	Medium	10	08.33
3	High	14	11.67
Farm Power Possession			
1	Low	46	38.33
2	Medium	62	51.67
3	High	12	10.00
Social Participation			
1	Low	28	23.33
2	Medium	86	71.67
3	High	06	05.00
Extension Agency Contact			
1	Low	44	36.67
2	Medium	60	50.00
3	High	16	13.33
Mass Media Exposure			
1	Low	36	30.00
2	Medium	66	55.00
3	High	18	15.00
Training Programmes Attended			
1	Low	42	35.00
2	Medium	70	58.33
3	High	08	06.67
Scientific Orientation			
1	Low	16	13.33
2	Medium	62	51.67
3	High	42	35.00

It could be observed from table 1 that half of the respondents (50.00 per cent) belonged to middle age category followed by 30.00 per cent of the respondents under old age category. Only 20.00 per cent of the respondents were found to be under young age. Most of the respondents belonged to middle age groups because of the reason that they might have the capacity to take the risk and solve problems with their adequate knowledge & experience in the entrepreneurial skills. This finding is in coincidence with the findings of Chithra and Meti (2018) who also reported that more than fifty per cent of the respondents belonged to the middle age category.

The table revealed that 30.00 per cent of the respondents had secondary education level followed by primary education (25.00 per cent) and higher secondary education (20.00 per cent). Functionally literate were 15.00 per cent of the respondents. Less than ten per cent of the respondents (06.67 per cent) were illiterate and had collegiate education (03.33 per cent). This may be due to, because the study area comprised majority of the families with poor economic status. This finding derives support from the findings of Jenila Stephency (2018) who also reported that majority of the respondents had secondary level education.

From the above table, it could be noticed that nearly three fourth (70.00 per cent) of the respondents had other subsidiary occupation along with mango cultivation. The 30.00 per cent of the respondents had crop enterprise alone as their occupation. During the survey, the researcher could observe that almost majority of the respondents had subsidiary occupations along with crop cultivation like rearing mulch animals, sheep and goat rearing, keeping poultry birds, etc., as they could earn an additional income from the subsidiary occupations, they looked after both farming and allied occupations to increase the family income. This finding is in line with the findings of Eswaran (2012) who also reported that majority of the respondents had subsidiary occupations along with farming.

According to the table, more than half of the respondents (55.00%) had a low level of annual income, while 35.00% had a medium level of annual income. Only ten percent of those polled had a high level of annual income. It can be deduced that the majority of respondents (55.00%) had a low annual income. In recent decades, the failure of the monsoon, a lack of market availability sources, and price fluctuations in mango may have been attributed as the main reasons for the low annual income. This finding is consistent with the findings of Vinoth (2012) who also reported that the majority of respondents had a low level of annual income.

It revealed that 58.33 per cent of the respondents had small farm holdings (2.51 to 5.00 acres) followed by 25.00 per cent of the respondents having big farm holdings (more than 05.00 acres). Only 16.67 per cent of the respondents possessed marginal farms (less than 02.50 acres). It could be inferred that majority of the respondents (58.33 per cent) possessed small size farm holdings of 2.51 to 5.00 acres. It was quite natural that large farm holdings are not necessary to cultivate mango in their own farm. Even in less farm size, a farmer can cultivate mango and get profit. The above finding had drawn the support, from Prakash (2016) who also reported that majority of the respondents possessed small farm holding.

The table revealed that around 65.00 per cent of the respondents had medium level of experience in mango cultivation, followed by low level 28.33 per cent and high level of experience in mango cultivation (06.67 per cent). It could be inferred that nearly two third of the respondents possessed (65.00 per cent) medium level of experience in mango cultivation. As discussed earlier, majority of the respondents were under middle age category, which might be responsible for the medium level of experience in mango cultivation. This result was contradictory with the findings of Karthikeyan (2017).

It could be revealed from table that more than three fourth (80.00 per cent) of the respondents had low level of area under mango cultivation followed by 11.67 per cent of the respondents with high level of area under mango cultivation. Only 08.33 per cent of the respondents had medium level of area under mango cultivation. It was quite natural that large farm holdings were not necessary to cultivate mango in the farm. Even in less acre of land, a farmer could cultivate mango and get profit. This might be due to the fact that most of the respondents had small farm size. This finding was in line with the findings of Jayasundar (2011).

It could be observed from the table that just more than fifty per cent of the respondents (51.67 per cent) possessed medium level of farm power, followed by 38.33 per cent of the respondents with low level of farm power possession. Only 10.00 per cent of the farmers possessed high level of farm power status. The mango growers take agricultural operation in only smaller proportion of their holdings. Hence it is not necessary to possess high cost farm power equipments. This might be due to the reason for the medium level of farm power possession. This finding also gets support from the findings of Sivaperumal (2013) who also reported that majority of the respondents had medium level of farm power possession.

It could be inferred from the above table that 71.67 per cent of the respondents had medium level of social participation followed by 23.33 per cent of the respondents with low level of social participation. Only 05.00 per cent of them had high level of social participation. As discussed earlier, majority of the respondents were under middle age group, and lack of awareness about the social organisations, absence of adequate number of social organisation in the study area and lack of time availability to the farmers might be the possible reasons for medium level of social participation. This finding is in accordance with that of Silambarasan (2015).

It could be revealed from the above table that two fourth of the respondents (50.00 per cent) had medium level of extension agency contact followed by 36.67 per cent respondents had low level of extension agency contact. Only 13.33 per cent of the respondents had high level of extension agency contact. From the results, it could be interpreted that fifty per cent of the respondents had medium level contact with extension agency, due to the partially visit made by extension functionaries to the farmer's field and the farmers visit to the office of the extension functionaries. From the above findings, it could be observed that majority of them possessed medium level of extension agency contact. The finding was in parallel with the findings of Aitochopi (2016) who also reported that majority of the respondents had medium level of extension agency contact.

The table revealed that 55.00 per cent of the respondents had medium level of mass media exposure followed by 30.00 per cent of the respondents with low level of mass media exposure in agricultural sector. Only 15.00 per cent of the respondents had high level of mass media exposure. Majority of the respondents possessed various media sources like newspaper, magazines, television and radio sets, but they were not frequently using these media sources for gathering agricultural information. It would have resulted for medium level of mass media exposure. This finding is in conformity with the findings of Vasanthakumar (2014).

The above data revealed that majority of the respondents (58.33 per cent) attended medium number of training programmes, followed by 35.00 per cent who have attended less number of training programmes. Only 06.67 per cent of the respondents attended more number of training programmes. On perusal of the findings it was found that majority of the respondents had received medium number of training. Training is one of the means by which desirable changes in knowledge, skills and attitude of entrepreneur could be brought. A trained farmer could manage his enterprise better and get more profits with high knowledge, which would contribute for increasing the socio-economic development in the rural sector. The finding is on parallel with the findings of Sindhu (2015) who also found that majority of them attended medium number of training programmes.

It could be seen from the table that 51.67 per cent of the respondents had medium level of scientific orientation followed by 35.00 per cent of the respondents with high level of scientific orientation. Only a less per cent (13.33 per cent) of the respondents had low level of scientific orientation. The reasons for the medium level of scientific orientation might be due to the

medium level of social participation and extension agency contact. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Gokul Pranesh (2017).

Conclusion:

The analysis concluded that the personal, socioeconomic, and entrepreneurial characteristics of mango growers revealed that the majority of respondents (50.00%) were middle-aged and had a formal education (78.33 per cent). They had secondary occupations in addition to farming (70.00%) and a medium level of experience in mango cultivation (65.00 per cent). They had a small farm size (58.33%) and a low annual income (55.00 per cent). They had a low area under mango cultivation (80.00%) and a medium level of farm power (51.67 per cent). They had medium levels of social participation (71.67%), extension agency contact (50.00%), mass media exposure (55.00%), training programme attendance (58.33%), and scientific orientation (58.33%). (51.67 per cent). Hence, it is necessary to improve their entrepreneurial performance by designing various Entrepreneurship Development Training Programmes (EDTPs) which were suitable for mango growers in Salem District. The characteristics namely, educational status, experience in mango cultivation, training programmes attended were found to influence the entrepreneurial performance of mango growers. Hence, these factors should be taken into consideration while formulating Entrepreneurship Development Training Programmes (EDTPs). These entrepreneurial characteristics of the mango growers may be improved with training, exposure visit and educational programmes and also by involving them in various development programme regarding entrepreneurial activities to develop their social- economic status in the rural area.

References:

1. Aitochopi, K. 2016. A Study on Knowledge and Adoption Behaviour of Rubber Growers in Dimapur District of Nagaland, Unpublished M.Sc., (Ag.), Thesis, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar.
2. Chithra, Y.D and S.K.Meti. 2018. A Study on Entrepreneurial Behaviour of Chickpea Seed Growers in Raichur District of Karnataka, India. The Mysore Journal of Agricultural Sciences, 52 (4): 796-803.
3. Eswaran, P. 2012. A Study on Entrepreneurial Performance of Farmers Practicing Mixed Cropping in Salem District of Tamil Nadu. Unpublished M.Sc., (Ag.), Thesis, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar.
4. Gokul Pranesh, M. 2017. A Study on Entrepreneurial Performance of Turmeric Growers in Erode District of Tamil Nadu, Unpublished M.Sc., (Ag.), Thesis, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar.
5. Jayasundar, R. 2011. A Study on Integrated Pest Management Practices by Sugarcane Growers, Unpublished M.Sc., (Ag.), Thesis, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar.
6. Jenila Stephency, T. 2018. Entrepreneurial and Marketing Behaviour of Coconut Growers in Kanyakumari District, Unpublished M.Sc., (Ag.), Thesis, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar.
7. Karthikeyan, T. 2017. An Analysis of Entrepreneurial Behaviour of Banana Growers in Tiruchirapalli District, Unpublished M.Sc., (Ag.), Thesis, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar.
8. Prakash, S. 2016. A Study on Knowledge and Adoption Behaviour of Banana Growers in Madurai District. Unpublished M.Sc., (Ag.), Thesis, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar.
9. Silambarasan, V. 2015. A Diagnostic Study on Precision Farming in Tomato. Unpublished M.Sc., (Ag.), Thesis, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar.
10. Sindhu, D. 2015. An Analytical Study on Turmeric Growers in Erode District of Tamil Nadu, Unpublished M.Sc., (Ag.), Thesis, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Madurai.
11. Sivaperumal, R. 2013. A Study on Precision Farming among Tomato Growers of Dharmapuri District, Unpublished M.Sc., (Ag.), Thesis, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar.
12. Vasanthakumar, K. 2014. Training Needs of Floriculture Farmers in Cuddalore District. Unpublished M.Sc., (Ag.), Thesis, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar.
13. Vinoth, J. 2012. Awareness, Knowledge and Adoption Behaviour of Coconut Growers in Theni District of Tamil Nadu- A Study, Unpublished M.Sc., (Ag.), Thesis, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar.